

THE ROLE OF COMPOSITE SYSTEMS IN LOWERING ENERGY INPUT IN CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract

Since 1975 UNIDO planned extensive programs on low cost housing , using less raw materials with low energy input and with the integration of local materials. A survey of the results obtained using fiber composites systems in the building sites of Cyprus , Ecuador, Mexico, Upper-Volta and Uruguay will be presented .

Three main problems had to be solved :

- adapt high technology to local circumstances and eventually jungle conditions, non skilled labour and absence of local energy and water supply .
- use the versatile properties of composites and make them able to work in combination with locally available materials.
- solve a double design problem consisting of creating a structure using less material and energy and offering maximum living space.

Basically the system uses an appropriate filament winding technology. The evolution of the machine to a light weight equipment is demonstrated and also the development of a housing structural unit of 15 m² habitability lowering the weight to 250 kg. Present results indicates in relation to normal construction a lowering to 1/50 in raw material and 1/20 in integrated energy input pro square meter. It is demonstrated that 30 m² high quality housing can be constructed in one day by six men .

ENERGY SAVING

Everyone is acquainted with concepts such as time, distance and speed, but not everyone is accustomed to handle energy units. Most people are not conscious of energetic values as they do not form a part of our intellectual and intuitive stock of knowledge.

One is usually not aware that every raw material requires an input of energy for its extraction, separation, purification, packaging, transport, stockage and marketing. From the energetic value of petrol one has to subtract the pumping, refining, cracking, transport, marketing, publicity, distribution, taking account the value of by-products, the waste management before arriving at its exact ratio to oil and thus being able to define the useful energetic efficiency.

Every consumer product is made from raw materials and each operation of manufacturing, publicity, selling, transport and even elimination of the product entails a consumption of energy. The sum of the energy needed for each operation is the integrated energy input. To obtain the integrated energy input per time unit, one has to divide by the life-time of the product. It is evident that energy saving can be realised in two ways: either by reducing the energy input or by increasing the life-time.

It has been calculated that the integrated input for a normal motorcar is nearly 5-6 times the total equivalent quantity of petrol that the car will consume during the whole period of its use without even considering the social costs or the transport infrastructure. So, here is an indication of the kind of topics we have to focus our attention on in an energy saving programme. One litre of oil contains approximatively 40 megajoules (10.000 kcal). A man can produce 2 megajoules (500 kcal) a day. The energetic value of one litre is thus nearly equivalent to the work produced by a man during a whole month. Manufacturing one dm³ of steel requires 10 litres of oil. This small quantity of metal is nearly equivalent to the work of a man during one year. A brick or a glass bottle corresponds to more than one week of human labour.

Considering the input by way of fertilisers, machinery, energy, transport etc. modern high production agriculture does not any longer produce the amount of calories that are put into the ground and consequently it has a negative energetic balance.

It becomes evident that each human activity and each consumer product uses up a lot of energy. Different events have given rise to alarm and have demonstrated that difficulties are imminent in the supply of energy. Authoritative opinions give warning that serious problems will arise before the end of the century and perhaps quite soon if the political climate is unfavourable.

This historic moment when technology makes it possible to be liberated from the constraints of labour and when the majority of the inhabitants of the planet could taken part in Western welfare, coincides with a period of shortage of energy and raw materials. The laws of Western economic system appear to lack the flexibility to escape from the dilemma. We must look for TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS.

Since 1971 United Nations Industrial Development Organization - UNIDO - is looking for solutions. A typical example of a product with high energy input, is housing. The construction of 370,000,000 dwellings, that have to be built in the next ten years, using traditional building methods would significate an ecological suicide.

So , it was decided to develop a " low energy housing system " suitable as an example for the development of other low energy products.

COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

Composite materials are developed from components on the basic assumption that the properties of the whole are different from and represent more than the sum of the properties of the components. The composite has one more important property : the relation between the components are more important than their intrinsic properties in determining the nature of the whole. The composite acquires a certain degree of independence from its components . A component having similar relation with the others may act as a substitute for the original in spite of its being different . Some examples may illustrate this.

An insulating material is composed of a binder, for example a polymeric matrix and air inclusions . The composite has insulating properties that cannot possibly be obtained from the separate components. Moreover it is possible to substitute PS by PU or any other polymer in the matrix. In the same way it could be possible to replace the air by any other inert gas , without changing very much the insulating properties of the whole. A fibre reinforced composite is developed from a matrix (polymer , cement, gypsum) and a reinforcing fibre . The mechanical properties of a fibre reinforced polyester do not allow any comparison at all with the properties of one of the components. It is now possible to develop alternative composites with other matrices and other fibre reinforcements, without changing the principle of the composite system . An insulating plate of foamed PU with its protective skin can insulate 25 times better than a brick wall of the same thickness and weight 750 times less. The application of a composite system , allows to lower drastically the amount of raw materials and the not renewable energy in doing this job.

It appears evident that we have discovered a methodology for the development of materials that allows us to escape from the traditional dependency: materials \longleftrightarrow properties . Till now , the raw materials used in construction have been limited to some restrictive classes : metals , ceramics, glasses and polymers . For example the materials are either good or bad conductors for electricity . Semiconductors are elaborated materials . It follows that some urgently needed properties are completely absent . We travel in space , but we lack the unbreakable , insulating , temperature and crash resistant material for our dishes . We are subject to a material dictatorship.

Nature has always used the composite principle . In structural applications : wood , bones . And man has imitated the model : reinforced polyester , metallic alloys etc. , but he has neglected to draw the final conclusions and to exploit this general principle to the root . It is probable that man's reluctance to accept the generalisation of the composite principle is linked with an instinctive fear of changing the thinking system .

Let us take the plunge . We are faced with a choice of materials that have increased their technological and intellectual qualities hundreds of times . But their properties are no longer determined and have to be reinvented for each application .

It is evident that for the development and the design of products out of composite materials , new creative methods have to be worked

out. Innovation in composite systems is not limited to adding and assembling elements . On the contrary , development of composite products tries to study and to understand global and integrated problems and to consider the components in their mutual relationship and the structure as a whole . Even traditional strength calculations has to be reconsidered . In most cases composite structures do not fail by lack of tensile or compressive strength of the material they are made of , but by stress concentration , influence of the environment , lack of fracture energy or by fatigue . These factors are usually more dependent on structural information, interactions and relations between the different components than on the specific properties of the material itself. In most cases design is more important than strength of material and instead of regarding the structure as an assembly of components suitable for calculation , one should study it as a global structural entity adapted to experiment

HOUSE CONSTRUCTION

Having this principle in mind , UNIDO planned a housing programme for developing countries . The construction had to meet following requirements : low cost , locally constructed , low energy and material input , high construction speed , use of non skilled labour, integration of locally available materials . The housing system had to be adaptable in case of emergency , in adverse building circumstances (e.g. without water and energy supply) and in cases of catastrophic events .

A serie of demonstration projects was carried out in Cyprus, Uruguay, Ecuador , Mexico and Upper-Volta , introducing each time new technical or architectural variables as sandwich construction , design improvements , mechanical strength of construction , variation in dimensions , use of natural fibre reinforcements etc .

The performance of fibre reinforced material in a given application depends to a large extent on the method of manufacture . Considering the requirements , an appropriate system of filament winding came out as the most adequate method to construct the insulated spaces of air needed for the building of dwellings . It allows to obtain a maximum strength of the structure , using a minimum amount of raw material . The shape of a housing module has been found to be perfectly suited to the process of filament winding . Composite construction of the walls can combine strength with high insulating properties . The high technology filament winding process has given the prove to be extremely adaptable to simplification . High quality pieces have been made on a hand driven machine .

The wounded shells have been manufactured on a locally made retractable rotational mould supported by an ax driven by hand by means of a crank and a reduction device . The fibres pass in a resin bath , laterally moving along the rotational mould distributing the wet reinforcement on the mould . The resin bath is a wooden support with a through away PE sack containing the resin . The excess of resin is pressed out by adjustable rubber strips that permit at the same time to adjust tension on the fibers .

STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOUR

It is worthwhile to examine the behaviour of the structure in sustaining loads . The structure is strengthened at both ends by two flanges . They have

a dual purpose . They are usefull in bolting the endwalls or one module to another . Structurally they act as a diafragm rigidifying the cilindrical shape .

Beam action in the longitudinal direction is neglectable ,because the module does not span between the flanges but is resting and sustained over its whole lenght in a bed of sand or stones . In that sence strenght and rigidity is only required during transport . On the contrary , the membrane action , typical in shell structures transmit loads axially . The strongest cross sectional shape in this respect is a circle . The greater the deviation from the circle , the lesser the structural strenght the better spacé demands . The flanges act in this respect as strenghtening elements . Present technology allows to adapt the quantity of strenghtening elements and to improve their design and to augment their dimensions . On that way it was possible to obtain a fantastic increase in rigidity and to eliminate any sagging after removal from the mould . Using this design method it could be possible to obtain even a rectangular shape , using of course more material to obtain the same strenght . The cross section can also be considered as an arch . The lateral stresses of the upper arch are taken over by the lower arch working as a flying buttress .

Beam action can also be observed in each segment of the curved panel . The forces of tension , compression and shear which are generated , could be accomodated by a sandwich construction . Its properties are dependend on the strenght of the upper and lower reinforced layers in resisting tensile and compressive forces and on the strenght and tickness of the sandwich structure determining its moment of inertia . The bond of the foam core to the two exterior layers is the most critical factor affecting the strenght of the whole structure . Taking into account local circumstances such as the nature and the quality of the insulating layer and the lack of equipment to maintain and control the quality of the adhesive bonds it was not advisable to rely upon the properties of the sandwich construction to obtain the necessary stiffness and strenght .

So, using reinforcing flanges and ribs it is possible not to be dependent on the sandwich construction . It allows were necessary to make a single wall shell . Insulating is indeed only justified when people are living inside at a different temperature than the outside . In other cases thermal confort is obtained by other means .

CONCLUSIONS

The practical conclusion is that a housing module can be built adjusting size, shape an proportion to every architectural design or environmental requirement . The closing panels , without strenght demands have been adapted in each project to local materials and local architecture .

In fact , only the structural body has to utilise the exceptional qualities of the reinforced composite . It is useless to squander an expensive material in applications where their properties are not used . Having this principle in mind , it is useless to put material under the ground in foundations and to deteriorate the soil . It is more logical to consider the structure as a floating element and put sheep ballast inside the shell , under the floor , as in a ship . At the same time , this mass of material is part of the thermal inertia of the whole construction . Once this technological solution has proved to be satisfactory in relating to its technical performances , we have to test its architectural and social

suitability .

It appears finally that the curved surface , obtained most easily by filament winding , is at the same time the form that uses the least material and energy , offers the highest mechanical strength and the largest living space . It is ergonomically best adapted to human beings and best suited to adjust itself to human and social requirements . It is thermally attractive because it offers a larger volume in relation with the surface exposed to outside climate .

In design technology, forms developed from global concepts often happen to fit esthetics and human values perfectly .

The use of composite materials has even opened the way for the use of local materials . At the last seminary of UNIDO in Quito -Ecuador - it was announced that in the CIQA laboratories in Saltillo - Mexico - similar strengths have been obtained with natural fibres as with glass fibres . These fibres are stabilised against bacterial attack and humidity .

It has been proved that unskilled people can handle completely the technology and build for themselves after a training period of no more than two months . Experiences have been performed in the open air and inside , in windy regions and tropical climates and even with differences of temperatures of 20°C in a few hours of time.

It has already been emphasised that synthetic polymeric materials in spite of the fact that they are oil derivatives are energy saving when the integrated energy input is considered . Furthermore, present experiment gives the proof that composite technology opens a new way to change drastically the usual way of wasting energy and raw material and to escape the dilemma between production and scarcity.

Present results can be summarised as follows :

- Weight input in relation to European construction : 1/100 and in relation to local brick construction in developing countries : 1/50 .
- The energetic input in relation to Europe is 1/20 and in relation to local construction : 1/10
- Speed of construction with equipment : 120 m² per 300/man hours .
- Price : 1/2 of local low cost housing .

There is good reason to believe that the energy input and the price can still be lowered substantially . On the other hand , it is clear already that the use of renewable raw materials and energy , the integration of locally available materials and of rural , industrial and domestic waste materials in composite systems opens unexpected future prospects .

1. Mould and filament winding unit for the Patfoort Housing System . View of the Ecuatorian plant .

2. Shell structure is removed from the mould and transported to the building site . One module is nearly 15 m² habitability and weights 250 kg

3. Inside view : high technology incorporating locally available materials such as bamboo and natural fibres.

4. Housing unit with solar protection in Huaquillas(Ecuador)

